

Lyapunov-Based PDU Set-Aware Scheduling for XR Traffic in 5G-Advanced Networks

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Abstract—EXTENDED REALITY (XR) applications place increasing pressure on mobile networks to meet their stringent Quality of Service (QoS) demands. In particular, XR services require high throughput and low latency, with traffic patterns that differ greatly from traditional applications. To address these challenges, we propose a novel Medium Access Control (MAC) scheduling solution that takes into account the segmentation of XR media units into Packet Data Units (PDUs), referred to as PDU sets in 5G-Advanced networks. These PDU sets correspond to the core traffic unit for XR services and must be delivered according to their specific QoS requirements, which are dynamically established in real-time by the XR application. The proposed scheduling solution leverages Lyapunov drift-plus-penalty optimization to jointly optimize resource allocation and stabilize traffic queues while ensuring the timely delivery of PDU sets. Our solution is implemented within the ns-3 5G-LENA framework, and the paper features a comparative analysis through extensive simulations, evaluating the performance of our proposal against existing MAC scheduling algorithms. Results evince that the proposed scheduler enhances resource utilization, ensures QoS compliance, and improves network performance.

Index Terms—5G, PDU set, XR, MAC, Lyapunov, ns-3

I. INTRODUCTION

In response to the challenges posed by new applications, with increasingly stringent QoS requirements, 5G networks have been designed to support a diverse range of services, each with its own performance needs. Beyond addressing the high capacity demands of Enhance Mobile Broadband (eMBB) applications, 5G must also accommodate the rapid growth of Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) and Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) services, which require support for a massive number of connected devices and extremely dependable, low-latency connectivity, respectively. 5G-Advanced, the upcoming evolution of 5G, is being developed to better address the complexities introduced by these next-generation services.

Among these, XR stands out due to its unique combination of requirements. XR devices are typically unable to locally manage all the required processing tasks and instead rely on support from external nodes. A common approach is split rendering, where the computational load of multimedia generation and augmentation is distributed between a high-performance XR server and the XR device. Processing-intensive tasks, such as scene rendering, are offloaded to the XR server, while lighter functions like pose correction are handled locally on the device. Furthermore, XR traffic ex-

hibits distinctive patterns driven by real-time user interaction, typically involving one or more DownLink (DL) video streams that must be tightly synchronized with frequent UpLink (UL) motion and control updates. Due to this interplay of high data rate demands and strict latency constraints, XR services might be placed between eMBB and URLLC in terms of network requirements, making them a key and unique use case for 5G-Advanced innovations.

In XR services, each media unit (such as a video slice or frame) is segmented into PDUs before being transmitted to users. On the client side, a minimum number of PDUs from each media unit must be received before decoding or further processing can take place. As a result, this minimum group of PDUs, referred to as PDU set in the 3GPP standards since Release 18 [1], constitutes the fundamental unit of XR service traffic, and should be therefore considered in resource allocation mechanisms, along with their specific QoS constraints.

The MAC scheduler is responsible for determining how radio resources are allocated among traffic flows. While 5G provides the architectural framework to support XR traffic, the standard does not define specific MAC scheduling algorithms, leaving their design and implementation open. In his seminal work [2], Neely introduced a comprehensive framework utilizing Lyapunov techniques for queue stabilization. This framework encompasses both max-weight (or min-drift) methods and the min drift-plus-penalty control problem. The approach not only focuses on stabilizing queues but also enables the integration of time-average objectives into the decision-making process. In particular, the Lyapunov drift-plus-penalty optimization is a well-established technique, which has been widely applied to queuing networks and other stochastic systems. It stabilizes real or virtual queues while simultaneously optimizing the network performance by minimizing the time-averaged network penalty function. In the context of MAC scheduling, we propose leveraging this methodology to design a novel PDU set-aware MAC scheduling mechanism to jointly optimize resource allocation, stabilize traffic queues, and ensure that the QoS requirements of XR services are met, taking full advantage of the new possibilities provided by the 5G-Advanced QoS framework.

Overall, the main contributions presented in this paper are:

- The proposal of a PDU set-aware drift-plus-penalty MAC scheduler that enhances the optimization of resource

allocation between demanding flows by considering the unique characteristics of XR traffic.

- The proposed scheduler achieves multiples goals, whose importance can be configured. We show that it is able to guarantee the specific requirements of every XR application, while ensuring an efficient use of allocated resources and the stabilization of RLC queues.
- We integrate the proposed MAC scheduler within the ns-3 5G LENA framework [3] and conduct a thorough performance evaluation against state-of-the-art scheduling approaches.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews relevant related work and highlights how our approach advances the state-of-the-art. Then, Section III provides background on 5G NR QoS management framework, with particular emphasis on the PDU set concept. Section V evaluates the performance of our proposed solution through simulations conducted in 5G-LENA, comparing it against alternative scheduling strategies under mixed XR traffic scenarios. Finally, Section VI concludes the work and outlines directions for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews recent contributions on MAC scheduling in 5G networks, with a particular focus on XR services, and identifies how this work differs from them, outlining its most relevant contributions.

Although research on QoS management for XR traffic in 5G NR is very active at the time of writing, existing studies related to MAC scheduling remain relatively limited. The authors of [4] propose a demand-based Proportional Fairness (PF) scheduler to differentiate between Virtual Reality (VR) and Ultra High Definition (UHD) traffic in eMBB scenarios. The QoS-aware scheduler in [5] performs traffic classification, including XR and mixed services, based on the associated 5QI. The authors of [6] introduce a scheduling strategy that combines channel and delay-weighted response ratios to manage heterogeneous real-time and eMBB traffic. Their method incorporates a prioritization function that accounts for proximity to the delay bound, packet size, and channel quality.

In addition, PDU set-based traffic handling is a relatively new concept, introduced under the umbrella of 5G-Advanced systems, and therefore existing literature on this topic remains very scarce. The few related works highlight the need for further looking into how PDU set-aware mechanisms can be leveraged for more efficient QoS management. The authors of [7] argue that the XR-aware cross-layer design in 5G-Advanced serves as a foundational step toward efficient scheduling of XR traffic, enabling initial performance gains in terms of data rates and low latency. Furthermore, they propose a delay-aware PF scheduler and demonstrate its performance gains compared to the baseline PF scheduler. Related to the latter one, [8] proposes a scheduler that exploits PDU set information to enhance QoS awareness. Instead of focusing just on individual PDU delays, the scheduler prioritizes the transmission of PDUs belonging to the same PDU set.

As we discussed in [9], our Lyapunov-based scheduling framework considers most of the metrics traditionally used by related works to address the scheduling problem, including channel quality, traffic stability, throughput and delay, while promoting the efficient utilization of radio resources. In this work, we include PDU set-awareness in the scheduling policy. To the best of our knowledge, this approach has been explored for MAC scheduling only by two of the aforementioned works, but with a more limited scope. Unlike these previous works, which focus mainly on PDU set features, our contribution provides a more comprehensive solution by incorporating a wider range of QoS metrics and adopting a novel approach to leverage PDU set-awareness. Thus, our work sets a clear advancement in the field, delivering a more holistic and efficient scheduling solution for real-time XR applications with stringent QoS requirements.

III. BACKGROUND

The 5G QoS model is structured around the concept of QoS Flows, supporting Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR) QoS flows, Delay Critical GBR (DC-GBR) flows (both requiring a specific Guaranteed Flow Bit Rate (GFBR)) and Non-GBR QoS Flows (which do not). A QoS flow represents the highest level of granularity for QoS differentiation within a PDU session. Each flow is identified by a QoS Flow Indicator (QFI), which is used throughout the 5G System (5G-S) to apply consistent traffic treatment, such as scheduling and admission control, for user plane traffic sharing the same QFI in a given PDU Session. The QFI is included in an encapsulation header over the N3 (and N9) interface, ensuring that end-to-end packet headers remain unchanged.

A QoS Flow is classified as either GBR, DC-GBR, or Non-GBR, depending on the characteristics defined in its QoS profile. Each QoS Flow is associated with a 5G QoS Identifier (5QI), which defines the treatment that traffic should receive across the 5G-S. A QoS profile includes, among others:

- **GFBR**. It specifies the minimum bit rate that must be provided to the flow.
- **Packet Delay Budget (PDB)**. It indicates the maximum delay that packets can experience between the UE and the UPF that terminates the N6 interface.
- **Packet Error Rate (PER)**. It defines an upper bound for the rate of PDUs that are processed by the sender at the link layer (e.g., RLC) but fail to be successfully delivered to the upper layer (e.g., PDCP) by the corresponding receiver within the Radio Access Network (RAN).

The 5QI can be either standardized or non-standardized (customized per operator needs). It plays a key role in enabling differentiated QoS handling across a wide range of services, including video streaming, VoIP, and XR applications.

Traditionally, QoS control in mobile networks has been based on two main concepts: flows and individual packets. However, scheduling approaches based on them overlook the interdependence between packets, which is a key aspect for interactive media services such as XR, where a single media-layer unit is often transmitted across multiple packets. To

Fig. 1. 3GPP XR DL video traffic model.

enable the integrated and differentiated transmission of media units (e.g., a frame or video slice), the PDU set concept is introduced in 5G-Advanced [10]. A PDU set represents the group of packets that collectively carry a media unit. All PDUs within a PDU set hold equal importance at the application layer. Furthermore, the application layer requires the complete set of PDUs to process the corresponding unit of information. However, in certain scenarios, the application can still assume a number of missing PDUs [11].

One of the most relevant traffic distributions is that of the video frame stream, whose pattern follows a truncated Gaussian distribution, which characterizes the size of media units, i.e. PDU sets, as well as the inter-arrival time jitter (in UL, jitter is typically neglected, since video is generated closer to or at the UE) [12]. Every PDU set is transmitted periodically with an average inter-arrival time equal to the inverse of the frame rate ($1/\text{fps}$), but subject to jitter. This must be carefully managed by the scheduler to meet the stringent delay and reliability requirements of XR services. Consequently, both the temporal dynamics and the size distribution of PDU sets are key factors influencing end-to-end QoS. Fig. 1 illustrates the XR traffic model, showing the aforementioned distribution.

The 5G Core (5G-C) acquires some information to support QoS handling at the PDU set-level that can be categorized in PDU set metadata and PDU set-level QoS parameters.

PDU set metadata:

- **PDU Set Sequence Number (PSSN) and PDU Sequence Number (PSN).** The PSSN represents the sequence number of the PDU set to which the current PDU belongs, serving as an identifier for the PDU set. The PSN denotes the sequence number of the current PDU within that PDU set.
- **End PDU indicator (EPDU).** It specifies whether the current PDU is the last one of the PDU set.
- **PDU Set Size (PSSize).** It corresponds to the total size, in bytes, of all PDUs of the PDU set to which the PDU belongs. This field is optional.

PDU set-level QoS parameters:

- **PDU Set Delay Budget (PSDB).** It specifies the maximum delay that a PDU set can experience during its transfer between the UE and the N6 termination point at the UPF. This delay is measured from the moment the first PDU is received (at the N6 termination point for DL or at the UE for UL) until all PDUs in the set have been successfully received (at the UE for DL or at the N6 termination point for UL).

Fig. 2. PDU set information transfer across 5G-S components to support QoS handling.

- **PDU Set Error Rate (PSER).** It defines an upper bound for the loss rate of PDU sets not related to congestion.
- **PDU Set Importance (PSI).** It sets the relative importance of a PDU set within a QoS Flow, compared to other PDU sets. This information can be used to discard packets at the PDU set-level during congestion. In general, higher priority is given to Intra-coded frames/slices over to P/B-frames or P/B-slices [11].
- **PDU Set Integrated Handling Indicator (PSIHI).** It indicates whether all PDUs of the set are required by the application layer at the receiver.

For QoS flows that use PDU set-based QoS handling, the 5G-C provides one or more QoS parameters (related to the PDU set) to the RAN. In particular, they are established by the Policy Control Function (PCF) and included by the Session Management Function (SMF) in the QoS profile provided to the RAN, being the original source of these parameters the XR application itself.

For DL traffic the User Plan Function (UPF) is required to identify the PDU sets and their characteristics, in particular the relevance and size of the PDU set. The UPF uses a Protocol Description that instructs how to do the identification for a traffic flow and subsequently inform the RAN of the associated PDU set information. Fig. 2 illustrates how information on the PDU sets is transferred across 5G-S, as was previously described. In addition, as can be seen in the figure, UPF maps identified PDU sets to QoS flows that require PDU set-based QoS handling, which are then mapped to Data Radio Bearers (DRBs) by the RAN. 3GPP defines the L:M:K notation to describe mapping configurations between (L) PDU sets, (M) QoS flows, and (K) DRBs. Due to limited visibility of PDU set information across protocol layers, only specific mappings 1:1:1, N:1:1, and N:N:1, are supported. The 1:1:1 mapping enables fine-grained QoS control per application stream, while the N:1:1 and N:N:1 mappings offer simpler coordination, by treating grouped PDUs with the same priority.

IV. SYSTEM MODEL

This section presents the design of the proposed scheduler and how it is integrated with the 5G-specific concepts introduced in Section III. The scheduler manages multiple traffic

queues, each associated with a specific 5QI, and potentially subject to a particular GFBR requirement and PDU set information. Let \mathcal{N} denote the set of queues. The objective of the proposed solution is to ensure queue stability, meet QoS constraints and, optionally, minimize overall resource utilization. For simplicity, we assume that each queue corresponds to a single UE. However, a more general formulation, mapping queues to Logical Channels (LCs), could be also considered.

We assume a slotted-time, and $Q_n(t)$ denotes the backlog of queue $n \in \mathcal{N}$ at time slot t , while $\alpha_n(t)$ represents the scheduling decision, i.e., the number of Resource Blocks (RBs) allocated to the n -th user. The system is influenced by stochastic factors, such as the Signal to Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR), denoted by $\gamma_n(t)$, and the traffic arrival to each queue, $a_n(t)$. The dynamics of each queue considers both arrivals and departures, $b_n(t)$, as follows:

$$Q_n(t+1) = \max\{Q_n(t) - b_n(t), 0\} + a_n(t) \quad (1)$$

In addition, we denote the instantaneous throughput perceived by the n -th user at time slot t as $\rho_n(t)$. As a result, both the incoming and outgoing traffic per queue, along with the user's perceived throughput, can be represented as general functions of the scheduling decisions and stochastic events:

$$a_n(t) = \hat{a}_n(\gamma_n(t)) \quad (2)$$

$$b_n(t) = \hat{b}_n(\alpha_n(t), \gamma_n(t)) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_n(t) = \hat{\rho}_n(\alpha_n(t), \gamma_n(t)) \quad (4)$$

Our goal is to ensure that a throughput requirement, Γ_n , for the n -th user, is satisfied on average over time. Thus, we consider the throughput time-averaged expectation $\bar{\rho}_n = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}\{\rho_n(t)\}$. The definition of Γ_n varies depending on the service type, as described in Eq. (5), where in the case of an XR flow with available PDU set information, the requirement is calculated as the minimum time-average throughput during the rest of the PSDB, which implies excluding the Head of Line (HOL), needed to ensure that the PDU set is delivered on time. For those flows without PDU set QoS, such as pose information or from non-XR UEs, the throughput target corresponds to the GFBR, if it is defined.

$$\Gamma_n = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{PSSize}_n}{(\text{PSDB}_n - \text{HOL}_n)} & \text{if XR with PDU set information} \\ & \text{and PSDB}_n > \text{HOL}_n \\ \text{GFBR} & \text{if GBR or DC-GBR} \\ 0 & \text{if PSDB}_n \leq \text{HOL}_n \text{ or non-GBR} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In addition, we aim to minimize the amount of allocated resources, being $f(t) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_n(t)$ the amount of RBs allocated at slot t . Since a greedy minimization of resources may hinder the throughput, we include, as an objective, the minimization of average allocated RBs, $\bar{f} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}\{f(t)\}$.

We enforce decision-making over a time-varying admissible action space, $\alpha(t) \in \mathbf{A}(t)$, ensuring that the number of allocated RBs does not exceed the amount available at each

time slot. Additionally, we define the throughput deficit as $D_n(t) = \Gamma_n - \rho_n(t)$, which satisfies $\bar{D}_n = \mathbb{E}\{\Gamma_n - \rho_n(t)\} = \Gamma_n - \bar{\rho}_n$. Overall, the scheduler tackles the stochastic optimization problem formulated in Problem 1, where constraint in Eq. (7) ensures that the throughput requirements are met. At the same time, the scheduler aims to maintain mean rate stability of the traffic queues, $Q_n(t)$ for all $n \in \mathcal{N}$, such that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbb{E}\{Q_n(t)\}}{t} = 0$.

Problem 1:

$$\min_{\alpha(t)} \bar{f} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \bar{D}_n \leq 0 \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha(t) \in \mathbf{A}(t) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Queues } Q_n(t) \text{ are mean rate stable } \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (9)$$

To address Problem 1, we adopt the framework outlined in [2], which extends the max-weight algorithm. Initially, we define a virtual queue $G_n(t)$ at time slot t , and its value is updated for the next time slot $t+1$, as follows:

$$G_n(t+1) = \max\{G_n(t) + D_n(t), 0\} \quad (10)$$

Now the problem can be solved by applying the *min drift-plus-penalty* algorithm [2, Chapter 4], which boils down to solving, at every slot, the following one:

Problem 2:

$$\min_{\alpha(t)} V \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_n(t) + \omega_Q \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Q_n(t)[a_n(t) - b_n(t)] \quad (11)$$

$$+ \omega_G \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} G_n(t) D_n(t)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \alpha(t) \in \mathbf{A}(t) \quad (12)$$

$$b_n(t) \leq Q_n(t) \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (13)$$

where the objective function comprises three distinct terms. The first one, designated as the *penalty*, aims to minimize the allocation of resources. The second and third terms correspond to the Lyapunov drift, which accounts for the stabilization of both traffic and virtual queues associated with throughput requirements. The penalty term is scaled by a design parameter, V , which governs the trade-off between minimizing resource usage and reducing queue backlogs. Furthermore, the traffic and virtual queues are weighted by coefficients, denoted by w_Q and w_G , respectively, to balance their influence on the scheduling decision.

V. EVALUATION

In this section, we discuss the performance of the proposed scheduler. The main goal of this evaluation is to assess the gain brought by incorporating PDU set information into the scheduling process. We compare our proposed scheduler to other PDU set-aware schedulers available in the literature [7], [8], the GFBR-aware scheduler from our previous work in [9] and a commonly used PF.

The performance of all schedulers is evaluated in a simple topology consisting of a gNB and several UEs, as outlined in Table I. In this scenario, all UEs generate XR traffic,

TABLE I
CONFIGURATION OF THE EVALUATION SETUP.

Parameter	Value
Application duration	60 sec.
Deployment	InH-OfficeOpen
Numerology (μ)	4
Carrier frequency	30 GHz
Bandwidth	100 MHz
gNB/UE Tx power	41 dBm/23 dBm
gNB antenna array	1 TXRU: 4 × 8 (3GPP elements)
UE antenna array	1 TXRU: 1 × 1 (isotropic element)
gNB/UE antenna element gain	8 dBi/0 dBi
gNB/UE noise figure	5 dB/7 dB
Noise power spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz
Duplexing mode	TDD

TABLE II
CONFIGURATION OF THE XR TRAFFIC.

Virtual Reality traffic		Cloud Gaming traffic	
5QI value	88	5QI value	3
Av. rate offered	45 Mbps	Av. rate offered	30 Mbps
FPS	120	FPS	120
GFBR	45 Mbps	GFBR	30 Mbps
PSDB	10 ms	PSDB	50 ms

specifically VR and Cloud Gaming (CG) flows, whose characteristics are described in Table II. As can be seen, VR traffic is configured with a more stringent QoS profile (5QI=88), corresponding to a DC-GBR resource type, while CG traffic uses the GBR resource type with a lower 5QI value (5QI=3).

Figs. 3 and 4 show the PDU set delay experienced by VR and CG UEs, respectively, in a scenario of 8 XR UEs in a cell. The delay is represented using boxplots, where the lower and upper edges of each box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The whiskers extend to 1.5 times the Inter Quartile Range (IQR), approximately covering the 2nd to 98th percentiles. Filled circles within each boxplot correspond to the average delay, while hollow circles represent outliers.

Schedulers are represented by a different color, resulting in one boxplot per UE for each scheduler. The proposed scheduler appears twice, corresponding to two different configurations: dark green for $V = 0$, which means no resource minimization is applied, and light green for $V > 0$, where the

Fig. 3. PDU set delay experienced by VR UEs under different schedulers. The dashed line indicates the PSDB.

Fig. 4. PDU set delay experienced by CG UEs under different schedulers. The dashed line indicates the PSDB.

Fig. 5. XR capacity as function of the number of UEs in the cell under different schedulers.

scheduler aims to minimize resource usage while still meeting the other objectives. In both cases, $\omega_Q = \omega_G = 1$.

A dashed line marks the PSDB, set to 10 ms for VR, and a more relaxed 50 ms for CG. As shown in Fig. 4, all schedulers meet the PSDB for CG traffic, except for a few out-of-time PDU sets ($\sim 2\%$) in the case of the PDU set-aware scheduler from [8]. However, this is not the case for VR. Fig. 3 shows that the PDU set-aware schedulers yield the best performance, consistently keeping the PDU set delay below the PSDB. It is worth noting that when resource minimization is active ($V > 0$) a few PDU sets exceed the 10 ms limit, but they represent less than 1% of the total. Among the other solutions, the GFBR-aware scheduler performs notably well, due to its prioritization of VR traffic based on its higher GFBR value. On the other hand, PF tries to balance throughput and fairness without explicitly considering QoS constraints, which results in worse performance for latency-sensitive VR traffic. Consequently, this traditional solution struggles to meet the stringent delay requirements imposed by the PSDB, reaching delays of up to 200 ms, 20 times higher than the 10 ms target.

The behavior observed for the different solutions is particularly relevant when considering XR capacity, which is the main Key Performance Indicator (KPI) defined in 3GPP Release 17 studies for XR services [12]. It is defined as the maximum number of XR UEs per cell for which at least 90% of UEs are considered satisfied, with a UE deemed satisfied if more than 99% of its frames or application-layer packets are successfully delivered within its PSDB. According to the simulation results, GFBR-aware solution and PF only manage to satisfy the CG UEs (i.e., 50% of the XR UEs in the cell) falling short of the 90% target. PDU set-aware schedulers from the literature increase the number of satisfied UEs, with 62.5% and 87.5% for DA-PF [7] and scheduler from [8], respectively.

Fig. 6. Average throughput within each 2-second window experienced by XR UEs under different schedulers. The dashed lines indicate the GFBRs.

On the other hand, the proposed PDU set-aware scheduling, in both configurations, achieves a 100% of satisfied UEs, making it the only solution that meets the XR capacity of 8 UEs. In this sense, Fig 5 shows the number of XR UEs satisfied as function of the total number of UEs in the cell, ranging from 0 to 12. A dashed line indicates the threshold above which the 3GPP-defined XR capacity is fulfilled.

Finally, Fig. 6 shows boxplots of the average throughput over each averaging window, i.e. 2 seconds, according to the standardized 5QI. The results are shown for 8, 10, and 12 UEs in the cell. For clarity, the UEs are grouped by the traffic type (VR or CG). As shown, in the least demanding scenario (8 UEs), all schedulers achieved similar throughput values, closely matching the GFBR (dashed lines). This proves that the improved delay performance achieved by the PDU set-aware scheduler does not come at the expense of hindering the compliance of the GFBR requirement. In the scenarios with 10 and 12 UEs, the average 2-second throughput per UE decreases, due to the total traffic increase. However, PDU set-aware schedulers manage to maintain 45 Mbps for VR UEs, due to the more stringent PSDB constraints compared to CG. This is not the case for DA-PF, which fails to sustain the same level of throughput for VR traffic under heavier load. This is in part due to configuration: the exponent of the PSDB metric [7] is not large enough to overcome the influence of the PF metric, which tends, in general, to equalize throughput among all UEs, as observed in the baseline PF scheduler. It is also worth noting that, by incorporating the RLC buffer occupancy into the scheduling decision, our PDU set-aware and GFBR-aware schedulers avoids buffer overflows, which the rest of the schedulers do not consider. This explains the observed outliers: 240 Mbps for PDU set-aware [8] and 90 Mbps for PF. The lack of buffer awareness also leads to fairness degradation.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced a novel PDU set-aware multi-objective MAC scheduler. To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the very few works that exploit PDU set-level information to guide scheduling decisions. By explicitly considering the delivery deadlines of each PDU set, the proposed scheduler ensures that the temporal constraints of

XR services are met, while maintaining queue stability and promoting efficient use of radio resources.

Our proposal has been implemented in the 5G-LENA framework. In contrast to existing solutions already available in the simulator, which lack fine-grained awareness of XR QoS requirements, our approach shows a consistent ability to meet XR delay constraints. Moreover, it enables a reduction in resource usage without compromising overall QoS fulfillment.

In our future work, we will continue leveraging the latest advances in QoS management introduced in recent 5G releases and envisioned for 6G networks. We plan to extend the scheduler's policies to incorporate additional QoS parameters and service-specific constraints, particularly for XR applications, enhancing the scheduler's adaptability and effectiveness across a broader range of traffic scenarios.

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